

CONVERTING TEST REQUIREMENTS INTO TEST PROGRAM SETS

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ABSTRACT

A new approach is described for converting a minimal set of test requirements and a set of test vectors into a working test program set (TPS). A test requirements file (TRF) expresses all of the necessary information for testing the logical functions and electrical and switching performance of a device-under-test. The TRF and the test vector files are processed automatically to produce the TPS. Test requirements are audited for correctness or reasonableness, and some types of tests can be generated automatically if their specifications are omitted.

INTRODUCTION

This paper describes the results of an in-house task performed at the Air Force's Rome Laboratory (RL) to generate test program set (TPS) data for digital microcircuits directly from high-level test requirements. The devices-under-test (DUTs) in this project were evaluation circuits developed under the Radiation-Hardened 32-Bit (RH32) Processor Program. The two RH32 contractor teams (TRW/UTMC and Honeywell) provided test vectors for the evaluation circuits in their own computer-aided design (CAD) and automatic test equipment (ATE) formats, along with "product specification"-style information such as pinout, functionality, and characterization data. Using this information, the RL test team implemented logic tests, as well as tests to characterize the devices' electrical and switching performance on RL's Teradyne J953 microcircuit tester.

Under the RH32 Program, the TRW/UTMC team delivered a "Pathfinder" chip in a 181-lead package with 141 I/O pins. Test vectors were provided in a single vector file in GenRad GR-18 format. Honeywell delivered a RICMOS IV "Evaluation Metal" chip in a 256-lead package with 210 I/O pins. The test vec-

tors were provided as trace files from Mentor Graphics Corp. QuickSim simulations for the individual macros on the chip; the timing conditions varied from vector file to vector file.

BACKGROUND

In general, a TPS consists of all of the components necessary to test a unit-under-test (UUT) or DUT using the target ATE. For equipment-level testing, MIL-STD-2077B [1] (summarized concisely by Dill [2]) defines these components as the *test program* (the code that controls the ATE), *interface device* (often called the *interface test adapter* or *test fixture*), and *documentation* (information about the TPS and the list of all items needed to test a UUT).

For microcircuit or chip-level testing, there are currently no TPS development standards other than the TISSS standards outlined later in this section. However, the basic components of a chip-level TPS are the same as for equipment-level testing, with the development of the test program being the most complex task.

For digital microcircuits, the test program is usually composed of three parts: the *test vectors* (binary or ASCII data that represent values or waveforms forced/measured on DUT pins), the *test application program* (executable or translatable code that controls the application of the test vectors), and *configuration data* (used to connect general-purpose test resources to the test fixture).

For many years, the Joint Army/Navy (JAN) Program has been the most widely-accepted approach for providing high quality and highly-reliable microcircuits.¹ In the simplest cases, Table I of a

¹The JAN MIL-M-38510 Qualified Parts List (QPL) Program [3] has been transitioned to the MIL-H-38534 [4] and MIL-I-38535 Qualified Manufacturers List (QML)

JAN detail specification (or "slash sheet") lists a set of designer's parameters or device characteristics; it resembles a product specification, and is usually derived from vendors' data sheets. Table II outlines the conditions under which tests of the characteristics listed in Table I are performed. Table III details the actual tests that are performed to guarantee each parameter listed in Table I, under the conditions listed in Table II. Each type of test is performed in accordance with the applicable method prescribed in MIL-STD-883 [6].

In the early 1980s the VHSIC Program sponsored the development of the Tester-Independent Support Software System (TISSS). The goal of TISSS was to automate the generation and maintenance of MIL-M-38510 test programs for complex VLSI/VHSIC devices, and to target multiple ATE types. Although TISSS is no longer active, there is active development of tools and data formats that have spun off from that program. Examples are tools for the IEEE's Waveform and Vector Exchange Standard (WAVES) [8] for test vector information, and generic postprocessors for generating test programs from the Test Requirements and Specification Language (TRSL) being pursued by ABBET (A Broad-Based Environment for Test) [7]. The interim TISSS tools support a Test Description Language (TDL) for the interchange of test program information; TDL is the strawman for TRSL until TRSL is defined. TDL is converted into test programs via the IN-STEP postprocessor.

RATIONALE FOR TEST REQUIREMENTS

An agreement was made that the in-house testing of the RH32 evaluation circuits would use the IN-STEP postprocessor and the WAVES translator for the J953 tester. This meant that the RH32 contractors' test vector sets and "product specifications" needed to be translated into WAVES vector data sets, TDL files, tester resource files, and interface identification files. Test programs would be written for a "virtual TISSS tester." The TISSS data would be processed through the interim translation tools and, using previously-developed J953 test templates, test programs would be created that would be compiled and run in the Teradyne environment. This process is shown in Figure 1.

The TISSS data formats are intended for the interchange of test data between test environments. There are several consequences of this: the data sets are large; the complex data relationships facilitate automated translation, but not human comprehension; the

Program [5].

strong typing of values and the checks of consistency and completeness mean that it is difficult to incrementally develop and debug a TISSS data set. As an example of the last point, both *addition* and *deletion* of a T_SETUP_TEST test macro in the TDL file may require editing of the CLOCK_PINS pin group definition in the PINS file. The authors chose to create the WAVES data sets by writing translators for the RH32 contractors' test vector formats, as well as developing a code generator to create the TDL data.

The TDL generator used as its basis a "golden" TDL file created and debugged by the authors for a simple CMOS dual d-flip-flop. The golden TDL file was dissected into code fragments that were used as templates for the translation program.

Since a translation process was to be performed, the opportunity existed to add both audit and test generation capability with a minimum of additional effort. The details of these capabilities will be given in a later section.

For input to the translation process, a data format called a test requirements file (TRF) was defined. A *requirements definition* approach was used to specify the desired values and tests; the product specifications were converted by describing *what* was to be tested, not *how* it was to be tested.² The notation for the TRF was intended to copy as closely as possible the standard terminology used in microcircuit specifications. For example, the V_{OH3} and I_{OL3} associated with a certain pin would be specified in the TRF as " $V_{OH3} = 3.0\text{ V}$ " and " $I_{OH3} = -1\text{ mA}$." The tool that converted the test requirements into TDL was called REQ_TO_TDL.

The TRF is completely non-procedural. Other than the sequentiality implied in the test vector set(s) specified in a TRF, no test ordering or setup conditions are specified. All of these considerations are accounted for in the golden TDL file and the native ATE templates that, in turn, implement the TDL. This was easy to implement in this case, because TDL is nearly non-procedural itself.

In TDL, there are essentially no default values: everything is fully specified. The TRF, on the other hand, is designed with the opposite philosophy: nearly everything gets a default value unless otherwise specified. Any pins that use the default values for voltages, currents, setup/hold times, etc., get the tests applied "for free." A similar approach had been used successfully in an earlier project at RL [9].

²The *how* part was embodied in the golden TDL file and the ATE templates that implemented the test programs on the J953.

Figure 1. Converting test requirements into executable test programs.

WAVES

The full expressive power of WAVES was not necessary for the testing of the RH32 evaluation circuits. In fact, only a small vocabulary of waveforms was sufficient to translate all of the given test vector sets. A few additional waveforms were defined to permit the systematic generation of switching tests. For example, a U waveform provided a positive pulse around the positive edge of the clock; this permitted t_s (setup) and t_H (hold) tests to be implemented in TDL/WAVES.

The set of WAVES characters implemented in this task is shown in Figure 2. Not shown in the figure are the WAVES character X, which indicates a masked (i.e., "don't compare") output pin, and N, which is a narrow clock pulse.

The WAVES characters shown in Figure 2 were more rigidly defined than they needed to be for implementation on the ATE. However, it was decided to conform to the rigid eight-event framework so as to make it possible to use the same vocabulary of WAVES characters in a logic and fault simulation environment.

The TRF approach was applied to the problem of testing a digital circuit for RL's Field Failure Return Program (FFRP). The DUT was the 54LS161 synchronous 4-bit counter [10]. It was also desired to verify the test vectors using a logic simulator.

WAVES is not yet directly compatible with widely-available digital logic simulators. However, it is a simple matter to break each WAVES frame into its component events and treat each event as a separate simulation cycle.

A WAVES_TO_PATS translator was developed to convert stimuli (expressed in the supported vocabulary of WAVES characters) into "flat" vectors for simulation. Each WAVES vector was broken into eight simulation vectors, where the U character, for example, would take on the string of values "01110000."

The logic model to be simulated was modified to add three-state buffers and an additional primary input to enable the buffers only during the eighth simulation cycle.³ Suppression of the output compare during the first seven simulation cycles was necessary so that the measured fault coverage would be based on the same data available to the ATE; this is in accordance with the requirements of MIL-STD-883 Procedure 5012, paragraph 3.4.1(a) [11].

The stimulus/response results from the logic simulation procedure were converted back into WAVES using a PATS_TO_WAVES translator. This tool reconstructed the WAVES characters by converting groups of eight simulation vectors at a time. For example, the stimulus string "00000000" was converted into the WAVES character 0, and the string "10001111" into D. The response strings "ZZZZZZ0" and "ZZZZZZ1" were converted into L and H, respectively.

The process of testing and verifying the FFRP device followed the flow outlined in Figure 3. First, the TRF and WAVES file for the DUT were generated by hand from the published military specification for

³When disabled, the three-state buffers force the primary outputs of the model of the DUT to the Z (high-impedance) state.

the device: M38510/315C, device type 04. The TPS created by this procedure worked on the J953 almost immediately. The only errors in the TPS turned out to be due to omissions in the printed copy of the device specification.

Next, a simulatable model of the FFRP device was created using RL's Netlist Intermediate Form (NIF) [12]. The NIF model was then translated into a Hierarchical Integrated Test Simulator (HITS) netlist. Using the WAVES_TO_PATS tool, the WAVES test vectors (including the timing tests) were converted into HITS format and simulated. In parallel with the logic simulation, the TRF and the WAVES vector file for the device were converted into eight TISSS files: TDL, PINS (part of the TDL description), and the six files that constitute a WAVES data set.

Finally, the output of the HITS logic simulation was converted back into WAVES using the PATS_TO_WAVES tool, and was shown to match the detail specification's predicted responses.

Figure 2. Basic vocabulary of WAVES characters.

TEST REQUIREMENTS FILE FORMAT

A complete example of a WAVES vector input file as used by the REQ_TO_TDL tool is given in Figure 4.

The corresponding TRF is given in Figure 5. The DUT in this example is a (fictitious) positive edge-triggered d-flip-flop. The pinout for the device is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Pinouts for d-flip-flop example.

Signal	Pin Type	Terminal	Waves Column
DATA	Input	Pin 1	1
CLK	Input	Pin 2	2
Q	Output	Pin 4	3
GND	Power	Pin 3	N/A
VDD	Power	Pin 5	N/A

The TRF is composed of four sections: *Files*, *Values*, *Defaults*, and *Pins*.

The *Files* section (prefaced by the string "FILES:") identifies the names of the TDL and WAVES templates to be used to build the output files, and identifies the prefix for the output files. This section also identifies the test vector files to be used to build the WAVES data sets; this example uses the same test vectors for the logic integrity, electrical, and switching tests, but three distinct files could have been specified. In this case, the input file will be DFF.PATS, and the six files that will constitute the WAVES data set will be DFF_XXX.WAV, where "XXX" is DUT, FRAMES, GENERATOR, HEADER, LOGIC, and PATTERNS.

The *Values* section (prefaced by the string "VALUES:") assigns the values from the product specification to the symbols used in the test program. A critical part of this section is the definition of the edges for the WAVES frames (reference Figure 2). Each of the WAVES characters is described in terms of a "from" and a "to" time aligned on edges shown in Figure 2. For example, the C character (generally used as a positive clock pulse) has its "from" time (corresponding to the rising edge of C) set to the value assigned to edge3; its "to" time (corresponding to the falling edge of C) is set to the value assigned to edge5. Characters used in pairs, such as U and D, can have their "from" and "to" times set in unison.

Note that there are two kinds of assignment: *symbolic* and *value*. An assignment is symbolic unless the value on the right-hand side is enclosed in curly brackets, which forces a lookup of the value assigned to the symbol referenced. For example, the statement "edge3 = 100 ns;" assigns the *symbolic* value "100 ns" to the symbol edge3. Then, the statement "waves_C.from = {edge3};" causes the value "100 ns" to be assigned to the symbol waves_C.from. If the curly brackets had been omitted, then the value "edge3" would have been assigned instead to waves_C.from.

Figure 3. Demonstration of simulation and test for FFRP device.

The *Defaults* section (prefaced by the string “DEFAULTS:”) associates the specific symbols (such as “VOH1”) with the generic symbols (such as “VOH”). Henceforth, if a V_{OH} test is performed, the default minimum value for the test will be V_{OH1} unless otherwise specified. Also in this section, test vector numbers are assigned the default value of “*” to force the appropriate test vectors to be found automatically for the voltage output and setup and hold tests.

In the *Pins* section (prefaced by the string “PINS:”) each DUT pin is described once. The description includes the name of the signal, the WAVES column, the terminal on the DUT package, and the test-related information. Data relating to a type of test are grouped in parenthesis, as demonstrated by the setup/hold tests and propagation tests in this example. Multiple tests can be specified with different values. The electrical tests are performed routinely with the default values. The timing tests must have at least the reference times and reference pins specified; defaults are used for the vectors.

TRANSLATION AND AUDITING OF TESTS

This section concentrates on the problem of generating the necessary test data (when they are not specified) from the information contained in the WAVES data sets, and the problem of auditing the validity of the test data that are supplied. Audits fall into two categories: *correctness*, where the translator can determine that the test is or is not performed, and

```

00X ;
01L ;
00L ;
10L ;
11H ;
10H ;
00H ;
0CL ; -- prop test for TPHL for Q
1CH ; -- prop test for TPLH for Q
DCL ; -- setup/hold test for 0 for DATA pin
UCH ; -- setup/hold test for 1 for DATA pin

```

Figure 4. WAVES example for d-flip-flop. Pin order is DATA, CLK, and Q.

reasonableness, where the translator can at most flag the fact that the test is not performed.

The current TISSS tools perform V_{OL}/I_{OL} and V_{OH}/I_{OH} tests by forcing a current and measuring a voltage on a given pin on a given test vector. A V_{OH}/I_{OH} test can be audited for correctness by ensuring that the specified pin has the value 1 (one of the characters “H+”) on the specified vector. A V_{OH}/I_{OH} test can be generated by locating the first vector on which the specified pin has the value 1, and inserting that vector number in the TDL code that implements the test. V_{OL}/I_{OL} tests are audited/generated similarly by looking for one of the characters “L-” associated with a pin.

V_{IL}/I_{IL} and V_{IH}/I_{IH} are tested "functionally" throughout the logic tests for the DUT. These tests are audited for reasonableness by checking that every input pin takes both of the values 0 (one of the characters "0CSIDBK") and 1 (one of the characters "1CTJUAK") at least once during the test. This is a check of reasonableness in the sense that if, say, the 0 value is not applied to an input pin, then V_{IL}/I_{IL} cannot have been tested for that pin.

Propagation (t_{PHL} and t_{PLH}) tests are performed for a measurement (output) signal with respect to a reference (input) signal. These tests can be audited for correctness by ensuring that two conditions are met. First, the reference signal must have a *legal input transition* (one of the characters "CSTJIUDABKN"). Second, the output pin must have a *legal output transition*: t_{PHL} requires a $1 \rightarrow 0$ transition (H or + on the previous cycle, and L or - on the current cycle), and t_{PLH} requires a $0 \rightarrow 1$ transition (L or - on the previous cycle, and H or + on the current cycle).⁴

Setup (t_S) and hold (t_H) tests (for both 0 and 1) are performed for an input "data" signal with respect to an input "clock" or "latching" signal that serves as the reference. These tests can be audited for correctness ensuring that three conditions are met. First, the tested pin (the data signal) must have a legal setup or hold transition on the measurement vector; *legal setup transitions* are "TDB" for 0 and "SUA" for 1; the *legal hold transitions* are "JDB" for 0, and "IUA" for 1. Second, the reference signal must also have a legal input transition. Third, at least one output pin must have a legal output transition ($0 \rightarrow 1$ or $1 \rightarrow 0$).⁵

Setup and hold tests can be generated automatically when a D or B is inserted in the test vector set for t_S/t_H for 0, and a U or A for t_S/t_H for 1. While this can be done manually, the WAVES translators developed for testing the RH32 evaluation circuits inserted these characters automatically. Using the "DBUA" characters allowed the test vector sets to be constructed modularly out of independent groups of test vectors. Otherwise, measurement vector numbers would have to have been revised repeatedly as modules were added and deleted.

STATUS AND FUTURE WORK

The TRF for the TRW/UTMC chip tests contained

⁴The test program generated from the TDL ensures that the output pin actually does depend on the input pin on the measurement vector. Otherwise, this would be an audit only of reasonableness.

⁵Again, the test program guarantees that the dependence exists.

962 lines, with the entire Pin section created automatically by the translator that converted the GR-18 test vectors. After the REQ_TO_TDL tool was run, the resulting TDL file contained 53,211 lines and the PINS file contained 1,082 lines. Counting only non-vector data, the total number of lines of "source code" for the WAVES data sets, TDL, and PINS files was 54,538, or 57 times the number of lines of code in the original TRF.

The same process for the Honeywell chip tests resulted in a 576-line TRF, again with the entire Pin section created automatically by the translator that converted the QuickSim trace files. Counting only non-vector data, the total number of lines of code for the WAVES data sets, TDL, and PINS files was 66 times the number of lines of code in the original TRF.

For the FFRP device, the ratio of non-vector lines of code was 20.1 to 1, and for the d-flip-flop the ratio was 21.3 to 1. Thus, the savings is greater for test programs for more complex devices. This ratio is expected to decrease when TRSL is implemented.

The TRF approach was particularly useful in developing the TPS for the Honeywell device because the test vector sets were provided as many independent modules. This technique allowed the TPS to be implemented and debugged incrementally, instead of having to trouble-shoot the entire TPS at once.

The REQ_TO_TDL, WAVES_TO_PATS, and PATS_TO_WAVES tools were written in PL/I running on a Data General Eclipse computer. Efforts are currently underway to port these tools as well as the TDL and WAVES tools to more standard Unix-based computing environments. The REQ_TO_TDL tool will evolve to accommodate changes to TDL and the planned transition to TRSL. It is also planned that translators will be built to create some native ATE test programs directly from the TRF.

CONCLUSIONS

This approach will dramatically reduce the amount of designing, coding, and debugging of TPS software required to test complex devices. Software development costs are generally assumed to be proportional to the number of source lines of code written; so far the TRF approach has provided approximately a 60-to-1 reduction in the number of lines of source code for actual TPSs.

The ability automatically generate some types of electrical and switching tests will allow test engineers to more easily perform incremental TPS development, which is a powerful tool for verification and validation of TPS software.

The computer system that hosts these tools is accessible via the internet. Interested parties may write to the authors or send them email (usernames are debanyw, koziarzn, and nagyj) at lonex.rl.af.mil.

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Figure 5. Complete TRF example for d-flip-flop. Two backslashes denote a line break.

FILES:

```
req = MASTER; -- (in) TDL templates
wav = MASTER; -- (in) WAVES templates
tdl = DFF;    -- (out) prefix for output files
```

-- Could have had three different pat files:

```
lit =      DFF; -- (in) logic integrity test
elec =     DFF; -- (in) electrical test
switching = DFF; -- (in) switching test
```

VALUES: -- symbolic values for TDL

```
cycle = 200 ns; -- ATE "cycle" time

VOL1 = 0.5 V; \ \    VOH1 = 2.4 V;
IOL1 = 32 mA; \ \    IOH1 = -12 mA;

IDD1 = 100 mA;
MAX_IDD1 = 500 mA; -- 5 times the spec value

VIL1 = 0.8 V; \ \    VIH1 = 2.0 V;
IIL1 = -5 uA; \ \    IIH1 = 5 uA;

TPHL1 = 10 ns; \ \   TPLH1 = 10 ns;

TS1 = 10 ns; \ \    TH1 = 2 ns;
```

-- Define edges for WAVES frames:

```
edge1 = 0 ns; \ \    edge2 = 75 ns;
edge3 = 100 ns; \ \  edge4 = 105 ns;
edge5 = 150 ns; \ \  edge6 = 155 ns;
edge7 = 175 ns; \ \  edge8 = 190 ns;
```

-- Assign WAVES events in terms of these edges:

```
waves_LH_from = {edge7}; -- compare for
waves_LH_to   = {edge8}; -- lo/hi
waves_C_from  = {edge3}; -- pos pulse
waves_C_to    = {edge5}; -- for clock
waves_UD_from = {edge2}; -- U: hi pulse
waves_UD_to   = {edge4}; -- D: lo pulse
CLK_POS_EDGE = {waves_C_from};
-- reference time for TS/TH tests
-- The rest of the WAVES characters are not used
-- in this example, but are provided anyway.
waves_ST_from = {edge1}; -- S: setup for 1,
waves_ST_to   = {edge2}; -- T: setup for 0
```

```
waves_IJ_from = {edge1}; -- I: hold: 1,
waves_IJ_to   = {edge4}; -- J: hold: 0
waves_K_from  = {edge3}; -- K: lo pulse
waves_K_to    = {edge5};
waves_AB_from = {edge2}; -- A: hi pulse
waves_AB_to   = {edge6}; -- B: lo pulse
waves_N_from  = {edge3}; -- N: narrow
waves_N_to    = {edge4}; -- pos pulse
waves_+_from  = {edge7}; -- here, same as
waves_+_to    = {edge8}; -- L and H
```

DEFAULTS:

```
VOH = VOH1; \ \    VOL = VOL1;
IOH = IOH1; \ \    IOL = IOL1;

VIL = VIL1; \ \    VIH = VIH1;
IIL = IIL1; \ \    IIH = IIH1;

IDD = IDD1; \ \    MAX_IDD = MAX_IDD1;

TS = TS1; \ \    TH = TH1;
TPHL = TPHL1; \ \  TPLH = TPLH1;

VOH_VEC = *; -- get 1st H or + in WAVES
VOL_VEC  = *; -- get 1st L or -
TS_0_VEC = *; -- get 1st D or B
TS_1_VEC = *; -- get 1st U or A
TH_0_VEC = *; -- get 1st D or B
TH_1_VEC = *; -- get 1st U or A
```

PINS: -- type can be INPUT, OUTPUT, INOUT, POWER

```
name = DATA, -- name of pin
type = INPUT,
pin = 1, -- column in WAVES file
term = 1, -- package terminal ident
(TS = TS1, TH = TH1, -- TS/TH times
TSH_REF_TIME = CLK_POS_EDGE, --TS/TH ref time
TSH_REF_PIN = CLK); -- TS/TH ref pin

name = CLK, type = INPUT, pin = 2, term = 2;

name = Q, type = OUTPUT, pin = 3, term = 4,
(TPHL = TPHL1, TPLH = TPLH1, -- prop times
TPHL_VEC = 8, TPLH_VEC = 9, -- vectors
TP_REF_TIME = CLK_POS_EDGE, -- prop ref
TP_REF_PIN = CLK);

name = GND, type = POWER, pin = 0, term = 3;

name = VDD, type = POWER, pin = 0, term = 5;
```